

Chinese Economic Development Under Deng Xiaoping

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Following the death of Mao Zedong in 1976, Deng Xiaoping (1904–1997) emerged as the dominant figure in Chinese politics. Born into a rural family, Deng joined the Communist Party in 1924 and participated in the Long March of 1934–1935. After the founding of the People's Republic of China in 1949, he rose rapidly through the ranks of the party, distinguishing himself by his pragmatism and ultimately leading the country's transformation toward a market economy—a transformation that has made China the world power it is today, and that enabled it to overcome the stagnation and scarcity that resulted from the Great Leap Forward under Mao's government.

The economic reforms during Deng Xiaoping's tenure were denominated the 'Four Modernizations'—promulgated in 1977—which sought to modernize the economy by adopting market-oriented policies while maintaining the fundamental principles of socialism, in accordance with the Four Cardinal Principles.¹ The objectives of the Four Modernizations included incentivizing foreign investment, the privatization of state-owned enterprises, and the creation of special economic zones—all of which gave rise to what is today referred to as the 'Chinese economic miracle.' (Britannica, 2021)

¹ The Four Cardinal Principles were enshrined in China's Constitution in 1982 and include: 1) Perseverance in the socialist path; 2) Perseverance in the people's democratic dictatorship; 3) Perseverance in the leadership of the Communist Party; 4) Perseverance in Marxism-Leninism and Mao Zedong Thought. (Xiaoping, 1979)

The First of the Four Modernizations focused on agriculture—an essential factor in a predominantly rural country such as China. In the early 1980s, a process of 'decollectivization' was undertaken by abandoning the system of agricultural communes and replacing it with family farms. These farms were granted long-term leasehold rights over rural property (for 15 or 30 years), which could be traded and inherited. Each peasant received a plot of land along with a production quota and inputs. Having fulfilled their objectives, the peasant could retain the resulting profits. This system, officially known as the 'Household Responsibility System,' drove significant advances in productivity and efficiency in land management, as each peasant had incentives to maximize their output.

The efficacy of this method proved, in some respects, to be in contradiction with several Communist principles, by adopting Adam Smith's notion that the pursuit of self-interest leads to the maximization of social benefits, while tending to set aside the Marxist idea of collective ownership of the means of production.

The increase in farmers' incomes stimulated demand for manufactured goods, attracted foreign investment, and thereby promoted industrial development. According to the Institute for Legal Research of the UNAM (n.d.), in 1981 agriculture represented 31.8% of GDP and employed 71%

of the labor force. By 2004, these figures had declined to 15.0% of GDP, with 56.9% of the labor force employed in the agricultural sector.

Second, Deng Xiaoping's government directed its attention toward foreign trade and the industrial production line, eliminating the isolationist policy implemented by Mao and establishing five special economic zones—which increased substantially over time—while broadening local authorities' powers to assess and authorize exports. In the 1980s, more than 90% of national production in China was controlled by state-owned enterprises. Through reforms introduced during that period, these enterprises were granted greater flexibility in production and investment decision-making, in addition to the commencement of a policy of price liberalization in areas previously controlled by the State. (Wilhelmy & Soto, 2000)

In 1984, additional reforms were implemented. Credit systems were established and export mechanisms through state intermediaries were designed. Remuneration systems based on marginal productivity were also introduced, and the transfer of state enterprises to local authorities began in order to improve their control and administration. Enterprise reforms continued in 1987 with the introduction of the Contract Responsibility System, whereby each enterprise signed an agreement with the government committing to pay a fixed annual tax. This allowed surplus profits to remain within the enterprise for distribution or reinvestment. These liberalization measures sought to improve the efficiency and productivity of enterprises, particularly impacting small and medium-sized business groups, where the relationship between effort and benefit for administrators was higher in comparison with larger enterprises facing greater redistributive pressures. (Instituto de Investigaciones Jurídicas, n.d.)

The transition from state-owned to private enterprises was not easy, and has been a central component of the transformation process in China, carried out in parallel with external opening and the attraction of foreign capital, for which various incentives were offered to investors—such as partial or total tax exemptions depending on the nature and duration of the investment—as well as full support for export- and technology-oriented enterprises. In addition, exemptions from customs duties and taxes were granted on imported machinery, equipment, parts, and components destined for the production of exportable goods, as well as on materials such as catalysts, molding materials, and oils imported for the manufacture of export products. Export duties were also waived and subsidies were facilitated for goods produced by foreign enterprises for export purposes. Other benefits included reduced input costs, inexpensive labor, and advanced infrastructure.

The gradual reforms were implemented to avoid the collapse of the state productive system and to bet on greater external competition to drive improvements in domestic productivity and exposure to the global market. (Instituto de Investigaciones Jurídicas, n.d.)

The Third Modernization referred to national defense, whose objective was to strengthen the military in order to protect the country from potential external threats. Investment was made in the modernization of the Chinese army, the procurement of weapons, and military research.

The Fourth Modernization focused on science and technology. Resources were increased for high-level schools and outstanding students were sent to the world's leading universities to study foreign culture and advances. Scientific education, research and development, and the transfer of foreign

technology were also promoted. These measures sought to foster the country's independence and self-sufficiency while simultaneously stimulating progress in production. (BBC, 2018)

In conclusion, the economic success of China can be attributed to the influence of Adam Smith's concept of the 'invisible hand,' above and beyond the Communist ideas of collectivization and price fixing—bearing in mind that the Four Modernizations promoted the privatization of state-owned enterprises and the liberalization of prices in various areas, which incentivized foreign investment. This, combined with tax reductions, inexpensive labor, and investments in research, development, and innovation (R&D+I), contributed to Chinese economic growth. With this in mind, it is possible to highlight that the Chinese model represents a syncretism of capitalism and communism, combining economic openness and a free market with the presence of a strong State that regulates and guides the economy. (Jabierto, 2017)

Furthermore, it is relevant to highlight that various sources—including the data presented in Table 1—demonstrate that Deng Xiaoping's policies lifted hundreds of millions of Chinese out of absolute poverty and set the People's Republic on the path to becoming one of the world's economic superpowers. However, it is important to consider the consequences of these policies, which unleashed an indelible effect on the Chinese environment, while also failing to ensure optimal working conditions for all workers—a high price to pay for the low cost of labor. (The Economist, 2023) In addition, one must not overlook the role of Deng Xiaoping's government during the Tiananmen Square massacre of 1989, with estimates of victims ranging between 200 and several thousand depending on the source (Clark, 2008)—revealing a complex and controversial historical legacy.

Table 1. Economic Advances in China (Instituto de Investigaciones Jurídicas, n.d.)

[See original document for table data]

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